

Bioremediation of Chromium

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Abstract

In the present study, biosorption of Chromium by microorganisms from Coal mine effluent was investigated. The initial concentration of heavy metal Chromium ($K_2Cr_2O_7$) in the effluent was 120mg/lit. The bacteria isolated from industrial effluent were identified as *Bacillus megaterium* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* by biochemical and 16S rDNA sequencing. The effect of pH and temperature on the biosorption capacity was investigated. Under the optimum conditions the highest uptake in pH 7 at 30°C was 96% and 90% in case of *Bacillus megaterium* and 95 and 90% in case of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. At low temperature and low pH the efficiency was reduced.

Keywords: Chromium, bioremediation, biosorption, effluent.

Introduction

Environmental pollution had been a fact of life for many centuries but it became a real problem since the start of the industrial revolution. Environmental pollution is one of the colossal problems of the world. It is increasing day by day due to industrialization. Over the last few decades large scale usage of chemicals in various human activities has grown very fast, particularly in India which has to go for rapid industrialization in order to sustain over growing large problem of population¹.

The current drift of industrial activity alters the natural flow of materials and introduces novel chemicals into the environment. The released inorganic compounds and heavy metals are one of the key factors that exert negative influences on man and environment causing toxicity to plants and other forms of biotics and abiotics that are continually exposed to potentially toxic heavy metals² of the various sources of pollutants.

Coal mine effluents containing heavy metals pose a threat to the ecosystem. These metals are also present in the waste water of different industries such as metal cleaning, plating baths, refineries, mining, electroplating, paper and pulp, paint and textile³. Water used in these industries creates a waste that has potential hazards for our environment because of the introduction of various contaminants such as heavy metals into soil and water resources⁴. Presence of pollutants in effluent is a common environmental hazard since the toxic metal ions dissolved can ultimately reach the top of the food chain and become a risk factor for human beings⁵.

It is also reported that contents of various chemical elements in soil affect the intensity of biological processes as heavy metal contamination of the environment is as well as deciding whether dietary intake of a given product is safe for Nogaj et al⁶ also stated that heavy metals are potentially toxic to crops, animals and human when contaminated soils are used for crop production because heavy metals are easily accumulated in vital organs of crops grown on these contaminated soils. Humans and animals that consume such crops are also prone to this potential toxicity⁷. This has really given impetus to the study on environmental problems of soil and water pollution by heavy metals in the last few decades⁸ with the development of an ecological geochemistry survey to aid in determining levels of heavy metal pollution and its potential risk. The major advantages of biosorption technology are their effectiveness in reducing the concentration of heavy metal ions to very low levels and the use of inexpensive biosorbent materials^{9,10}. Hence the present study explored the properties of *Bacillus megaterium* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in the remediation of Chromium.

Material and Methods

Collection of Sample: Effluent sample was collected in the plastic containers from the outlet of Margherita coal mine in Margherita in Tinsukia district in the Indian State of Assam. Its various physico-chemical characteristics were analyzed using standard methods¹¹. The effluents were stored at 4°C during storage period to avoid changes in its characteristics.

Atomic absorption spectrophotometric method: The estimation of chromium in the effluent was performed as per standard method. Three concentrations of each standard metal solution were selected to find out the expected metal concentration of a sample. Then each standard was aspirated into flame and the absorbance was recorded. A calibration curve was prepared by plotting the absorbance of standards versus their concentrations. The estimations of chromium were done at the wavelengths of 357.9 nm.

Calculation: The concentration of each metal ion was calculated in milligrams per liter by referring to the appropriate calibration curve.

Isolation and identification of chromium resistant bacteria: For isolation of chromium resistant bacteria, samples were serially diluted in sterile phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) and spread inoculated onto Nutrient agar amended with 50 µg/ml of chromium. A filter sterilized solution of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ was used as the source of chromium which was added to the sterile molten Nutrient agar to prevent

problems associated with autoclaving chromium containing solution. The effluent sample directly streaked on nutrient medium and incubated at 37°C for 24 h. After the incubation period the plates were observed for growth on the media. Colonies obtained were picked and purified by many round of re-streaking. Two isolates were selected for further studies. Microscopic and biochemical tests were applied to this isolates according to Bergey's manual of systematic bacteriology. The genres to which the isolates belong were determined. 16S rDNA sequencing also has been performed to identify the strain.

Growth of microorganisms and Biosorption: *Bacillus megaterium* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was incubated at 37°C and at 150 rpm for 24 hrs in Nutrient broth. At the end of incubation, biomass was separated from medium by centrifuging at 5000 rpm and it was kept in the oven at 50°C to remove the free water as much as possible. Then it was suspended in deionized water separately in order to use it in the biosorption. 2ml of culture were initially supplied with 120mg/l of K₂Cr₂O₇ separately to the sterilized medium and incubated at 30°C for 60h. 100 mL solutions containing 100 mg/L were prepared from stock solution containing 1g/L K₂Cr₂O₇. Adsorptions of metals were investigated for different pH values adjusted by using HCl and NaOH at 37°C. The solution containing the biomass was agitated in a shaker of 150 rpm during the adsorption. Samples taken at predetermined intervals were centrifuged and supernatants were analyzed. The analyses of chromium ion were carried out by atomic adsorption spectrophotometer (Perkin- Elmer) at 0.01 ppm sensitivity level after dilution of the samples¹². By taking the determined optimum conditions into consideration, the capacity of microorganism to remove the mentioned metal from the effluent sample was searched with the same method.

Results and Discussion

Some physico-chemical characteristics of effluent were ascertained from where chromium tolerant bacteria were isolated. The colour of the effluent sample is brownish black, temperature is 36°C and pH is 5.8. When subjected to AAS, total chromium was estimated to be about 120mg/L. Chromium resistant isolates were identified as *Bacillus megaterium* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* according to Bergey's Manual of Systematic Bacteriology and 16S rDNA sequencing. Both isolates exhibited high resistant to chromium. From the optimization study, it was noted that at pH 7 *Bacillus megaterium* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* showed 114.3mg/l and 105 mg/l biosorption activity. At pH 8 the results noted were 77.8 mg/l and 91.5 mg/l followed by pH 6, 94.5mg/l and 88.5mg/l, at pH 5, 67.5mg/l and 51.2 mg/l. Similarly at temperature 30°C the biosorption level noted was 112.5 mg/l and 104.7 mg/l, at 35°C the biosorption level noted was 108 mg/l and 99.3 mg/l at 40°C biosorption level is 83.8 mg/l and 86.8 mg/l at 25°C it was 78.4 mg/l and 94.5 mg/l.

Dextrose as a carbon source highest heavy metal reduction efficiency has been shown in table 6. Ammonium chloride as nitrogen shows highest reduction rate (Table 7). The results showed that pH 7 and temperature 30°C were found to be optimum for both spp for the biosorption study (Table 1 and 2). From the optimization study the effective pH 7 and temperature 30°C for 24 hours (Table 9) were maintained in coal mine effluent for *Bacillus megaterium* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The efficiency of the results noted was 95 and 88%. In general, potential micro-organisms especially bacterial species can remove heavy metals from solutions by biosorption or bioaccumulation or both. A variety of mechanisms exist for the removal of heavy metals from aqueous solution by bacteria, fungi, ciliates, algae, mosses, macrophytes and higher plants^{13,14}.

Biosorption largely involves physical adsorption followed by chemical bondage and does not require energy. Once, the metal ions are diffused on the cell surface, they bind to sites which exhibit chemical affinity for the metal. It is a passive accumulation process which may include adsorption, ion-exchange, complexation, chelation and microprecipitation. During the present investigation *Bacillus megaterium* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* both were found to be highly resistant to chromium. Under the optimum conditions (Table 1 and 2) the highest uptake was 96% and 90% in case of *Bacillus megaterium* and 95 and 90% in case of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* for both the strain. Hence both bacteria not only exhibited the ability to survive in contaminated wastewater but also demonstrated a marked increased in remediation of toxic Cr in their presence.

Conclusion

The present study establishes the role and efficiencies of *Bacillus megaterium* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in the adsorption of chromium in coal mine effluents. The technology when upgraded will be a boon to industrialist in tackling the pollution problem of mine waste water. The process would not only be economical but also eco-friendly and sustainable. However, further research is needed to establish the process with specific attention.

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Table 1
Effect of pH on biosorption of Cr mg/L by *Bacillus megaterium* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

S. N.	pH	I. C* of Cr(VI) (120 mg/l)			
		<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>		<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	
		F.c*	E*	F.c*	E*
1	3.0	111	26	102	32
2	4.0	90.4	40	93.2	38
3	5.0	52.5	65	68.8	54
4	6.0	25.5	83	31.5	79
5	7.0	5.7	96	15.0	90
6	8.0	42.2	72	28.5	81
SED		4.6953		1.1173	
CD(P=05)		10.2357		2.4357	

I. C*: Initial Concentration; F.c*: Final concentration; E*: Efficiency (%)

Table 2
Effect of temperature on biosorption of Cr mg/L by *Bacillus megaterium* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

S. N.	Temp* °C	I. C* of Cr(VI) (120 mg/l)			
		<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>		<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	
		F.c*	E*	F.c*	E*
1	20	52.5	65	60.2	60
2	25	41.6	72	25.5	83
3	30	7.5	95	15.3	90
4	35	12.0	92	20.7	86
5	40	36.2	76	33.2	78
6	45	44.8	70	49.5	67
SED		1.5853		1.7230	
CD(P=05)		3.4559		3.7562	

I. C*: Initial Concentration; F.c*: Final concentration; E*: Efficiency (%)

Table 3
Morphological and biochemical characteristics of heavy metal tolerant bacteria

ISOLATES	HEAVY METALS (mg/l)				
	K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇				
	50	100	150	200	250
<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	+	+	+	+	+

Table 4
Growth of bacterial strains at different concentration of heavy metals (Cr mg/l)

Colony character	Colony Morphology	Cell Morphology	Gram staining	Spore staining	Motility	Starch hydrolysis	Gelatin hydrolysis	Casein hydrolysis	Catalase test	Oxidase test	Indole test	MIR test	Citrate utilization test	H ₂ S Production	Nitrate reduction	Urease test	Probable organism
Cream color	Irregular	Short rods	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>
Slimy	Flat	Short Thick rod	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	-	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>

Table 5
Antibiotic sensitivity profile of heavy metal tolerant bacteria

S.N.	Antibiotics (10µg)	Diameter of inhibition zone (cm)	
		<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
1	Gentamycin	1.2	1.4
2	Kanamycin	0.8	1.1
3	Streptomycin	1.6	1.8
4	Chloramphenicol	0.9	1.2

Table 6
Effect of different carbon sources of bacterial isolates on heavy metals reduction

S. N.	Carbon sources	I. C* of Cr (120 mg/l) I. C			
		<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>		<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	
		F.c*	E*	F.c*	E*
1	Dextrose	17.8	88	27.3	82
2	Fructose	30.2	80	33.0	78
3	Maltose	25.5	83	28.8	80
4	Sucrose	21.1	86	31.5	79
5	Cellulose	42.3	72	48.2	68
6	Starch	25.4	83	45.3	70
SED		1.0550		0.6513	
CD(P=05)		2.3000		1.4198	

I. C*: Initial Concentration; F.c*: Final concentration; E*: Efficiency (%)

Table 7
Effect of different nitrogen sources of bacterial isolates on heavy metals reduction

S. N.	Nitrogen sources	I. C* of Cr(VI) (120 mg/l)			
		<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>		<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	
		F.c*	E*	F.c*	E*
1	Peptone	39.0	74	45.0	70
2	Beef extract	57.0	62	59.6	60
3	Yeast extract	33.2	78	36.0	76
4	Ammonium nitrate	45.3	70	54.2	64
	Ammonium chloride	17.6	88	30.4	80
6	Ammonium sulphate	27.4	82	37.5	75
SED		2.2109		0.6238	
CD(P=05)		4.8199		1.3599	

I. C*: Initial Concentration; F.c*: Final concentration; E*: Efficiency (%)

Table 8
Effect of different level of inoculum load of bacterial isolates on heavy metals reduction

S. N.	Inoculum load	I. C* of Cr(VI) (120 mg/l)			
		<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>		<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	
		F.c*	E*	F.c*	E*
1	0.5	57.3	62	59.8	60
2	1.0	46.5	69	52.6	65
3	1.5	32.9	78	39.4	74
4	2.0	6.2	96	12.1	92
5	2.5	6.4	96	10.2	93
6	3.0	7.5	95	11.8	92
SED		0.0545		0.0964	
CD(P=05)		0.1188		0.2101	

I. C*: Initial Concentration; F.c*: Final concentration; E*: Efficiency (%)

Table 9
Effect of different incubation time of bacterial isolates on heavy metals reduction

S. N.	Incubation time (hours)	I. C* of Cr(VI) (120 mg/l)			
		<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>		<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	
		F.c*	E*	F.c*	E*
1	6	96.4	36	102	32
2	12	67.5	55	74.7	50
3	18	40.5	73	48.0	68
4	24	15.2	90	20.8	86
5	30	14.8	90	21.5	86
6	36	15.4	90	24.3	84
SED		0.0724		0.2475	
CD(P=05)		0.1579		0.5396	

I. C*: Initial Concentration; F.c*: Final concentration; E*: Efficiency (%)

Table 10
Heavy metals reduction efficiency percentage under optimum condition

S. N.	Optimized parameters		Heavy metal reduction efficiency (%)	
			Chromium	
			<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
1	Carbon source	Dextrose	88	82
2	Nitrogen source	Ammonium chloride	88	80
3	pH	7.0	96	90
4	Temperature	30	95	90
5	Inoculum load	2.0	96	92
6	Incubation time	24 hours	90	84

Fig. 1: Growth of bacterial isolates in Nutrient broth under various chromium concentrations

Fig. 2: Growth curves of *Bacillus megaterium* in metal supplemented and metal free nutrient broth

Fig. 3: Growth curves of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in metal supplemented and metal free nutrient broth

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